

DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGY-INTEGRATED JUST-IN-TIME TEACHING WITH PEER INSTRUCTION PEDAGOGY FOR ACTIVE LEARNING IN MATHEMATICS.

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Abstract:

Mathematics is a significant part of our daily lives, yet adolescent students develop a dislike for mathematics. Maths educators must focus on teaching styles that cater to today's digital natives and make the subject more meaningful, engaging and relevant for them. The present research paper aims to develop and validate Technology-Integrated Just-in-Time Teaching with Peer Instruction, an active blended learning pedagogy in Mathematics for Upper Primary students. The strategies will be developed in alignment with the SAMR model for technology integration. The overall Active Learning Technology-Integrated Pedagogical design will be based on the IPSIT Model to empower students with crucial, relevant and contemporary mathematical skills.

Keywords: just-in-time teaching, peer instruction, SAMR model, IPSIT model

1. Introduction

Mathematics is a significant part of our lives, yet many students do not consider math as their favourite subject. Students find it difficult to solve mathematical problems and develop a dislike for them. Inferences can be drawn from previously conducted studies that only teaching mathematical content conventionally is insufficient to resolve these issues of fear and dislike towards Maths. Math instructors must also focus on pedagogies that influence the way the students engage in classrooms, which eventually leads to better achievement in Mathematics, inspires them to take Maths courses and Maths-related careers in future. (Ariyanto et al., 201,7). In today's digital age traditional style of teaching Maths is becoming increasingly redundant as the Internet gives flexibility to educators and students to connect and learn beyond the four walls of classrooms (Mepo, 2024)

National Curriculum Framework (2000) emphasises experiential learning in Mathematics. National Curriculum Framework (2005) aimed at the mathematization of a child's thought processes, correlating it with daily life experiences for children to enjoy Mathematics. The NEP (2020) recognises the pertinent role that mathematics plays in shaping modern careers and leadership positions. It stresses developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills in Upper Primary grades. These students are expected to use the dispositions from the Preparatory stage and be introduced to diverse forms of understanding. The Pedagogy methods are expected to meet the needs of the present century. The teaching methods should not focus only on recollection of facts, but on developing a sense of inquiry and leading to a deeper understanding of the concepts taught. The emphasis should be on students gaining systematic knowledge, logical thinking, and problem-solving skills.

The National Curriculum Framework (2023) aims to help students appreciate the internal beauty of Mathematics and value it. The content of Mathematics should encourage students to find utility in

abstraction and develop critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. One of the major goals of Mathematics education is to make students realise that one may face struggles while solving problems and try various methods to find the correct solution, but once understood and seen holistically, it can be stored away and used just as a step when needed. This perception is one of the joys of learning Mathematics, and efforts should be taken to introduce students to it (NCERT OFFICIAL, 2023).

Thus, to fulfil the demands of the 21st-century education ecosystem, technology-integrated pedagogy is an essential component to be included in it. The assimilation of technology in Maths pedagogy enables learning to be more relevant, engaging, student-centric, and collaborative (Tobondo, 2025).

Theoretical Framework

In the Educational ecosystem, Instructional models provide educators with a systematic, research-based structure that helps to design, implement and evaluate learning experiences to help students achieve set learning outcomes(Jha, 2022) . Some of the popular models for integrating Technology and Blended learning are 1) ADDIE, 2) ASSURE, 3) TPACK, 4) Flipped classroom, etc. All these Instructional design models are suitable for active and blended learning environments. These models focus more on course development and guide the process of the lesson. For the present study IPSIT model for the overall Instructional framework and the SAMR model for technology integration were chosen. IPSIT and SAMR are teaching-learning models that are designed specifically for the classroom-level pedagogical intervention with reference to technology-inclusive, subject-specific learning outcomes, suitable especially for Mathematics. ISPIT, being an Indian Framework model, is more adaptable to Indian classrooms adopting NEP2020 directives. ISPIT works seamlessly with SAMR to integrate technology at various phases. Hence, ISPIT and SAMR models were found to be more apt for achieving the objectives of the present study.

Active Learning Technology-Integrated Pedagogy (ALTIP)

To make Maths learning more effective, our students need to be more active participants rather than just passive receivers in learning environments. Active learning methods enhance knowledge transfer and foster metacognition skills, enabling learners to reflect on their abilities (Active Learning | Centre for Excellence in Teaching and Learning, 2021). In this digital-native student era, we must develop instructional strategies that make Mathematics education more inclusive, modern, and meaningful.

Blended Learning (BL)

The new NEP aims to take an educational policy that is student-centric and aspires to achieve Education 4.0! It promotes diverse forms of student-centric learning and shifts its focus to BL. It recommends the use of BL at all levels for all courses, from school to higher education (Fitri et al., 2019; Kaur, 2023; Kumar, 2010; UGC Concept Keynote for Blended Learning). A well-crafted BL provides a smooth transition from classroom to computer and vice versa, and expects a systematic blend of meaningful activities in both modes that mainly considers student-centred learning objectives in a structured learning environment. BL provides opportunities for students for collaboration between students and teachers and amongst themselves, flexibility, enriched learning, and efficient training to be digital citizens (Fitri et al., 2019; Kaur, 2023; Kumar, 2010)

IPSIT Model: An Indian Framework

For blended learning designs, the University Grants Commission of India has proposed the IPSIT Model, consisting of five phases:

1) **Identify Resources and Learner-Centred Activities** – Blended learning is a meaningful blend of virtual and real learning environments. Teachers planning to implement BL need to identify and plan resources for online and offline activities in corresponding environments for smooth execution

2) **Provide resources and announce activities on LMS** – A concrete digital environment is imperative for the implementation of such a meticulous plan. LMS with e-resources for announcement of diverse online tasks becomes an important component of BL

3) **Scaffolding and Support to Learners** -BL requires the teacher to act as a facilitator. Continuous scaffolding is necessary as the learner engages in active learning in student-centric classrooms. The discussions, resolution of queries, and construction of knowledge will be sought under the guidance of a teacher

4) **Identification of learning gaps and feedback** – Learners must be made aware of their progress on their learning path for effective learning. Periodical formative assessments, quizzes, projects, and presentations will help to identify the gaps in learning.

5) **Testing: assessment and evaluation** – Testing of all levels of learning outcomes needs to be systematically executed. Teachers need to come up with innovative evaluation techniques and not just “recall” tests in the name of Summative evaluations. (Naveen, 2021)

SAMR Model

SAMR Model, created by Dr Ruben Puentedura in 2010, is a design framework for integrating technology to improve Instructional strategies. This 4-level hierarchical technology usage Model is an Acronym for Substitution, Augmentation, Modification, and Redefinition.

- ☐ Level 1 -**Substitution**: As the name suggests, traditional tools are replaced by technology tools with no functional change.
- ☐ Level 2 – **Augmentation**: There is a functional change along with the addition of technological tools
- ☐ Level 3 – **Modification**: Technology significantly modifies the task to allow more collaborative, engaging and inspiring work.
- ☐ Level 4 – **Redefinition**: Technology relates the task to the real world to make it more meaningful and which was previously implausible.

Just-in-Time Teaching (JiTT)

The Just-in-Time Teaching approach was invented by Gregor Novak, Professor of Physics at Indianapolis in the 1990s. JiTT, as a blended active learning method, has gained popularity and has been widely implemented for various educational disciplines. It is designed to enhance learning outcomes and promote student engagement (Abreu & Knouse, 2014). It uses the feedback loop between web-based materials students use to prepare at home before class and classroom activities. In this strategy, students are expected to do a pre-class activity assigned, then respond to carefully constructed digital assignments that are pending before class. These assignments help the learners to engage with the content and identify their challenges. The teacher reads the responses shortly before class. Thus, pre-class formative assessments provide a window into a student's mind, help the teacher identify the gaps in learning and fine-tune their in-class activities accordingly. The instructor adapts his teaching “just in time” according to students' needs and resolves their difficulties. (*Just-in-Time Teaching (JiTT)*, n.d)

(Image: sketchbubble.com)

Peer Instruction (PI):

Peer instruction as a teaching tool was developed by Harvard Professor of Physics, Dr Eric Mazur, in 1991. It is a student-centred pedagogy where students act as teachers to each other. Students need to have clarity of concepts in their minds. They should be able to reframe the language to teach their classmates. This leads to reinforcement and a better understanding of topics for themselves. It enhances student engagement, reduces anxiety, promotes interest, and fosters deeper learning in students. It aims to involve learners in taking responsibility for actively constructing their knowledge.

The steps of Peer Instruction are:

- 1) The Teacher introduces the content concisely
- 2) The Teacher asks a conceptual question that is designed to provoke critical thinking and discussion
- 3) The students individually give responses after thinking about it
- 4) Students discuss among themselves their responses in small groups, which allows them to explain the rationale behind those responses.
- 5) Students get an opportunity to re-record their responses
- 6) The Teacher presents the solution and provides explanations addressing any common doubts or misconceptions. (Kaymak, 2022).

The goal of the PI is to help students solidify their own understanding as they help their peers understand the concepts. It boosts students' active engagement, collaborative learning, and higher-order thinking skills

JiTT combined with PI, efficiently provides students and teachers with background knowledge during pre-class tasks, responses, and follow-up discussions. JiTT helps the instructor know gaps in students' learning. The adaptable nature of PI allows the instructor to utilise time to narrow down on concepts that are difficult to understand and help students achieve conceptual clarity. PI and JiTT can boost the metacognitive abilities of students as they check their own understanding of topics during pre-class activities and in-class questions. JiTT and PI combination provides personalised learning as JiTT questions and in-class tests can be customised to a variety of learning objectives (Mazur & Watkins, 2023).

Technology-Integrated Just-in-Time Teaching with Peer Instruction of Mathematics (TI-JiTT-PI-M)

In this study, the Technology-Integrated Just-in-Time Teaching with Peer Instruction of Mathematics (TI-JiTT-PI-M) is an instructional approach that seamlessly integrates to enhance the mathematical learning experiences. In this method, the educator employs online platforms, such as interactive maths software or learning management systems (Google Classroom), to deliver pre-lecture reference materials, quizzes to students before the scheduled class. These digital resources are carefully designed to address specific mathematical concepts or skills that will be discussed during the upcoming session.

Before the in-class session, the instructor reviews student responses and identifies areas of confusion or common misconceptions through real-time data analytics provided by the technology. Peer Instruction is then employed, where students engage in collaborative discussions or peer teaching to clarify doubts and reinforce their understanding of the mathematical concepts. The operational goal of this approach is to use technology to provide just-in-time learning materials that encourage student preparation and active engagement, leveraging peer interaction to promote deeper comprehension and retention of mathematical principles.

Review of Related Literature:

Past studies' results reveal that Active learning using SAMR models increases student attendance and engagement in classrooms and provides advantages to students from weaker backgrounds and females (Freeman et al., 2014; R, 2009). Kaur(2023) examined the effects of blended learning on the Mathematical Achievements of Grade 9 students and found them to be more impactful. Naveen (2021) has emphasised in his study to adopt IPSIT framework to promote 21st-century learning

skills in Indian classrooms. Abreu & Knouse (2014) have summarised well in their studies the benefits of adopting JiTT to improve motivation and critical thinking skills for STEM subjects. Baish(2012) and Chowdhary (2020), in their Quasi-Experimental studies in Maths and English, respectively, have proved that Peer Instruction produces significantly greater results in learning achievements

Review of the Related Literature reveals that no study in India has been done using JiTT as one of the treatment variables or on the IPSIT model as an instructional framework in schools. For Peer Instruction, few independent studies have been conducted, but it has never been taken as a combination with JiTT, especially for Upper Primary students.

Hence, the present pedagogy was developed after identifying a crucial gap in the literature.

Objectives:

Consequently, the following objectives were sought:

- 1) To identify Active Learning Technology-Integrated pedagogy for Mathematics for the Upper Primary stage.
- 2) To develop a Technology-Integrated Just-in-Time Teaching with Peer Instruction of Mathematics (TI-JiTT-PI-M) pedagogical strategy for the Upper Primary Stage
- 3) To validate the TI-JiTT-PI-M pedagogical strategy through expert review

2. Methodology

2.1 Development of TI-JiTT-PI-M Pedagogy

The development of pedagogy was based on a Constructivist approach, allowing students to co-construct their knowledge through scaffolded inquiry and peer discussions. This approach was led by active learning and blended learning principles to promote student engagement and peer collaboration. The ISPIT model was used to structure systematic blended learning instructions, and the SAMR model was used to decide the level of technology integration.

2.1.1 Rationale behind the selection and design of the units

The first stage involved an analysis of the review of related literature, as well as the syllabus and textbook of Mathematics of Grade Eight (upper primary stage) prescribed by the Maharashtra State Bureau, to decide the steps of the pedagogical strategy to teach Mathematics

On careful analysis of the textbook, four units, 1) Discount and Commission, 2) Quadrilateral: Construction and its properties, 3) Equations in one variable, 4) Statistics, belonging to different branches of Mathematics, 1) Arithmetic, 2) Geometry, 3) Algebra, 4) Statistics respectively were selected, providing a holistic plan to evaluate pedagogical adaptability. All four units provided scope for conceptual diversity, real-life applications, competency-based education, and were relevant to 21st-century learning skills, corresponding with the goals of NEP 2020 of technology integration, providing experiential, collaborative, and higher-order learning in Mathematics. (Goel, n.d.; Mazur & Somers, 1999; Novak et al., 1999)

2.1.2 The Design of the Pedagogical Strategy of the Four Instructional Units

The design of the pedagogical strategy based on TI -JiTT-PI-M for each of the four instructional units from the Grade Eight Mathematics textbook is now described as follows:

Each unit lesson plan was divided into 2 phases:

Phase	Teacher Activity	Student Activity	Framework Integration
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<p>Pre-class Activity (JiTT)</p>	<p>The teacher posted an introductory video /interactive PPT for each unit in Google Classroom,3-5 days before commencement of actual teaching. The e-resource focused on the foundation required for that particular unit, for students to recall previous knowledge, to understand its importance and correlate with real life. There was an online quiz at the end of each video for the teacher to understand the gaps in students’ learning. Students were encouraged to post their doubts/ comments on the material</p>	<p>The student studied the e-resources, attempted the quiz and left a comment/doubt reflecting a sense of inquiry.</p>	<p>IPSIT Phase: Identify & Provide, SAMR Level: Substitution, Augmentation.</p>
<p>In-class Activity (Peer Instruction)</p>	<p>The teacher commences the class with a question identified from the gaps in learning obtained from pre-class activities. The teacher plays the role of facilitator in class activities</p>	<p>Student actively participates in Group discussions, role-plays, group quizzes, hands-on activities, etc., that lead them from incorrect answers to correct solutions of the problem.</p>	<p>IPSIT Phase: Scaffold, Integrate & Test, SAMR Level: Modification/ Redefinition</p>

The IPSIT model served as the overall-encompassing framework, ensuring seamless transition between the two phases, while SAMR guided technology integration levels. JiTT-PI, in unison, paved the way for Active Learning.

2.2 Validation of Instructional Units

These instructional units were developed based on conceptual, empirical, and literature available in the fields of mathematics education, active learning, and blended learning pedagogy. After preparing the TI-JiTT-PI-M draft, the researcher carefully reviewed it. The researcher obtained the opinion of experts in the field of education and mathematics pedagogy for evaluating the instructional relevance. The pedagogical strategy for each of the four units was then modified according to the discussions held with the research supervisor and experts’ suggestions.

3. Conclusions

This paper aimed to develop and validate a pedagogical strategy based on TI-JiTT-PI-M to teach upper primary stage students. The paper delineated the development of pedagogy and the rationale behind it. The work of planning was conducted with all possible care and attention, keeping in mind the capacities of upper primary students, and the spirit of technology-integrated active blended learning strategies alive throughout the process.

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